

CS Track introduces new models for analysing citizen science activities

The CS Track team has released a new report entitled **Models to identify background factors associated with the CS activity**. It introduces the analysis of the CS Track survey, summarises the characteristics of citizen scientists, discusses how learning and knowledge building occurs, and explains the structure of and the basis for the proposed models.

CS Track researchers selected 6 different CS activities from the survey data (N=1,083), that illustrate the diversity of CS projects. Citizen scientists reported their participation in 1) collecting data, 2) retrieving scientific literature, 3) discussing results, 4) training or guiding others, 5) organising activities, or 6) providing resources to solve complex simulation problems.

For each of these 6 activities, an analysis of the survey data was conducted to examine which project-related and personal factors explain (as well as help us predict) the likelihood of participating in project activities. That is, if a significant score for a project-related and/or a personal factor was assigned to an

activity by respondents, then that factor was added as a predictive factor for the activity. The goal of these **6 models is to help us understand and link different background factors together to create meaningful and relevant interpretations**. In Figure 1, CS Track researchers illustrate how statistical modelling will construct an explanatory model of a particular phenomenon. For example, the factor “How long the respondent has been engaged in CS activities”, was significant in all six models. In other words, it was significantly related to all six activities in question. Furthermore, if the respondent had been engaged in CS for 10 years or more, we can estimate that he/she had participated in data collection activities with probability of 0.940, according to Figure 1. Figure 1 shows

Figure 1. Models to identify background factors associated with the CS activity

only a fragment of the results, but it highlights some of our final findings (which are to be published in a peer-reviewed journal). One such finding was that "how long engaged" was systematically associated with all six activities, while factors like "age" and "gender" did not appear significant in all six models.

The proposed models are used to deepen our understanding of citizen scientists' backgrounds and their involvement in citizen science activities. The acquired knowledge will be used together with other data collected by the CS Track team members to create policy recommendations and thus determine accreditation practices.

Download the full report [here](#).

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